

PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT OF PULPITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH THE VITAL METHOD

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Abstract

Caries, which is one of the current problems in stomatology, is an open source of infection of the body, and if not intervened in time, leads to a deeper process - pulpitis, though it occurs in up to 3% of cases during pregnancy, most often it may lead to various complications of pregnancy, risks of premature birth, premature peeling of the pair and spread of infection. Taking into account the relevance of the topic, among 22 pregnant women diagnosed with pulpitis, treated with devital method, 58% were in the second trimester, 33% were in the first trimester, and 9% were in the last trimester. At the same time, the course of pregnancy of these patients, the development and condition of the fetus, and the presence or absence of extragenital pathologies of women were kept under control. As a result of the examination, in 8 pregnant women, incorrect treatment of etiological factors was detected and corrected, embalming paste (Devital-C) was used in 2 patients, 9 pregnancies ended successfully, and pregnancy continued normally in 3 patients. Thus, timely correction of the oral cavity, especially of carious teeth, of all women planning to become pregnant will enable future pregnancies to end normally.

Keywords: pulpitis, caries, vital pulp, pregnancy, crown pulp, carious cavity, peridont, preparation

Introduction. Pulpitis is an inflammation of the tooth pulp. It makes up 14-25% of dental diseases. The frequency of occurrence in pregnant women is up to 3% [1].\

Causes:

Against the background of a decrease in resistance, inflammatory reactions develop in the pulp as a result of the passage of a high concentration of pathogenic microflora through the channels of the dent.

Traumas are divided into 2 parts - chronic and acute. Chronic injuries develop over a long period of time as a result of incorrect installation of orthopedic constructors, high restoration of antagonistic teeth. Acute traumas include injuries [1, p.2].

Physical effects of overheated tips during preparation-turbine tips become very hot and irritating to the pulp if not used continuously with water.

Caries is divided into 3 levels: superficial, medium and deep. If it is not treated in time, the process worsens and turns into deep caries, followed by pulpitis.

In a retrograde way, the elements in the inflammation center formed in any part of the body can join the blood circulation and cause pulpitis in the oral cavity.

During diffuse inflammation in periodontal tissues, the infection can spread to the surrounding tissues and cause pulpitis in the teeth.

Bruxism is a disease in which the teeth rub against each other involuntarily. At this time, as a result of physical effects, the pulp may become irritated and stimulate pulpitis (1,4,6).

The idea that "the mother's teeth are demineralized during pregnancy" is considered completely wrong. There is no clear scientific evidence that this is true (TDB) (3).

The main causes of tooth decay during pregnancy:

- the mother, whose gums bleed more quickly due to the effect of pregnancy hormones (estrogen, progesterone),

- avoidance of brushing her teeth
- increased desire for sour and sweet foods during these periods

- lack of attention to oral hygiene after vomiting in the first months

- increase in the amount of acidity in saliva during pregnancy.

- In the period of puberty (sexual maturity), carious, pulpy teeth, inflamed gums, dental cysts have a negative effect on the function of a number of organs, including the gonads, which causes ovarian dysfunction in girls, resulting in a decrease in fertility.

- Studies have shown that one of the causes of ovarian cysts and retardation of sexual development even in girls is chronic gingivitis and caries.

- Inflamed teeth in pregnant women are an active infection gate for the fetus. Thus, any pathogen that enters the oral cavity can easily pass through the fetoplacental barrier and enter the fetal body through the blood circulation of the couple, which results in various pregnancy complications - premature separation of the couple, premature flow of amniotic fluid, miscarriages, and the risk of premature birth. [1, p.3].

Clinic:

- Pain caused by irritation or spontaneous onset
- Hypersensitivity to heat and cold
- Tartar can form
- Bad breath
- Complications include fever and swollen lymph nodes
- Widening of the periodontal fissure (chronic)

□ Microabscesses appear, blood vessels expand sharply, capillary stasis is detected (acute purulent). [2,4,6].

Differential diagnosis:

Spontaneous onset of pains at night without acute pulpitis-irritation effect.

Chronic pulpitis-causing previous pain in the tooth, changes in the periodontal cleft.

Probing hypertrophic pulpitis is painful and acute bleeding is observed.

Gingival swelling - probing is painless and there are no signs of inflammation. (2)

Treatment tactics:

A number of principles should be considered during dental interventions during pregnancy:

PERIODS (trimesters)

- First trimester (8-12 weeks) - the fastest period of organogenesis. Risk of spontaneous abortion.

- Second trimester (13-24 weeks) - organogenesis is completed. The most suitable period for dental interventions.

- The third trimester (25-40 weeks) increases the risk of premature birth after the first half.

ANTIBIOTICS

□ In systemic abscesses, progressive infections (spreads to surrounding tissues within 24 hours), weakness, fever, etc. instructions for use in cases.

Side-effects:

- Tetracycline(D)
- Doxycycline(D)
- Metronidazole(C) (according to some authors)

Can be used:

- Penicillin 500mg(B)
- Amoxicillin 500mg(B)
- Clindamycin 150-300mg(B)
- First dose 1mg/6-8h interval (3).

When symptoms improve and signs of recovery are seen, antibiotic intake should be stopped and re-examination should be made after 2-3 days. (2,3,5)

ANESTHETICS

ARTICAIN (C) HCl-4% w/1:100 000epi Max. Dose 7.5mg/kg

MEPIVACAINE (C) 3% 30mg/ml Max. Dose 7mg/kg

LIDOCAINE (B) 2% (with and without epinephrine)

The most reliable anesthetic in pregnancy.

The letters shown next to the preparations indicate the degree of danger in pregnancy by the International Food and Drug Administration (FDA). (3,5).

X-Ray

Although x-rays are not considered dangerous in dentistry, they should be used in minimal doses and as few times as possible during pregnancy (especially the first trimester).

A lead apron should be worn.

For less X-rays, canal lengths should be determined with the Apex Locator.

The biological method is aimed at healing the damaged pulp and restoring lost functions.

Three different categories should be considered for vital pulp based on clinical signs:

These are: normal pulp, pulp that results in complete healing, and non-healing pulp.

In the treatment of vital pulp, it is recommended to use sodium hydrochloride (NaOCl) in order to control the risk of bleeding, easily remove the blood clot and excess dentin, and create conditions for the formation of a dentinal bridge (5,7).

Surgical treatment is divided into two parts: vital and devital:

The Devital method consists of first devitalizing the pulp and then removing it. For this purpose, pastes containing arsenic and paraformaldehyde are used. Because these pastes can irritate the tissues around the tooth, their use during pregnancy is limited.

Surgical treatment with the vital method is divided into 2 parts:

- 1) Vital pulpotomy - amputation of the pulp. At this time, only the damaged part of the pulp is removed.

- 2) Vital pulpectomy-extraction of the pulp. The pulp is completely removed.

Treatment scheme:

- 1) Anesthesia is performed.

- 2) It is insulated (with a rubber roof).

- 3) Carious cavity is prepared.

- 4) Crown pulp is removed.

- 5) Access to channels is provided.

- 6) Working lengths are set.

- 7) Rotary is expanded by switching to files.

- 8) It is irrigated at each file change (NaOCl-2%; EDTA-17%; Distilled water) and finally channels are activated.

- 9) Channels are dried using "Papers".

- 10) It is obturated by lateral and vertical condensation.

- 11) It will be restored in the next visit. (3,5,7).

The purpose of the study. Taking into account the relevance of the mentioned problem, we have set ourselves the goal of studying the principles of treatment of pulpitis in pregnant women with the vital method.

Clinical material and examination methods. During the study, 22 pregnant women with pulpitis were examined. Pregnant women mainly complained of pain, increased sensitivity and difficulty in feeding due to this. During the examination and treatments, the duration of pregnancy, the presence of extragenital diseases in women, the course of pregnancy, and the condition of the fetus were monitored.

Approximately 58% of patients presented in the 2nd trimester, 33% in the first trimester, and 9% in the last period of pregnancy.

*Picture 1. Patient reports: 21 st week of 23 year of pregnancy
Diagnosis: 2.7 and 3.7 th irreversible pulpitis/calculus in teeth*

*Picture 2.
Post-obturation X-ray view of restoration of teeth with pulpitis and root canal obturation in the same patient.*

The application frequency of examined women according to the duration of pregnancy is presented in scheme 1.

Figure 1. Frequency of referral of examined women according to the duration of pregnancy

As a result of the examination, it was found that the etiological factor of the disease in 8 pregnant women was previously improper treatment.

In 2 patients, no numbness was achieved in the initial intervention. An embalming paste (Devit-C) was used to avoid further anesthesia.

The pregnancy ended successfully in 9 patients.

Pregnancy in 3 people continues normally.

Picture 3. Patient data: 31 years/18 weeks of pregnancy. Complaints: nocturnal pain due to irritation and spontaneous onset

Diagnosis: irreversible pulpitis in tooth 4.6.

Picture 4. Channels extended to 35/04. It was irrigated and obturated.

Thus, as a result of the conducted examinations and anamnestic data, recommendations were prepared for all pregnant women in order to prevent stomatological problems that may occur during pregnancy and to create conditions for the birth of a healthy child.

Result:

1) A proper diet must be observed (not eating at night, limiting colored and carbonated drinks, refusing "Fast Food")

2) Avoid bad habits.

3) Take proper care of teeth after every meal.

4) The intake of medicinal preparations and nutritional supplements should be strictly controlled (teas with various herbal ingredients, uncontrolled long-term intake of vitamin and Fe preparations)

5) Examination of the oral cavity before pregnancy and treatment if necessary.

6) Dental education should be given seriously to pregnant women in women's clinics.

References:

1. R.M. Mammadov, A. Ch. Pashayev, B. M. Hamzayev, V. M. Hasanov Therapeutic dentistry. Baku, 2017.
2. Hasanov V.M. Therapeutic dentistry: basic knowledge. Baku, 2010.
3. Scientific articles of the Turkish Dentists Association: Pregnancy dentistry., 2016.
4. Hasanov V.M. Therapeutic dentistry: diseases of the hard tissues of the tooth.. Baku, 2012
5. Seyidbeyov O.S., Abishov R.G., Imanov E.E. Local anesthesia in dental practice. Baku, 2009
6. Ibrahimova M.Kh. Ibrahimov Z.O. Propedeutics of therapeutic dentistry., Baku, 2010
7. Morotomi T, Washio A, Kitamura C. Current and future options for dental pulp therapy. Jpn Dent, Sci Rev 2019;55(1):